

CONTROL OF THE SKILLS AND ABILITIES OF THE STUDENTS

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ANNOTATION

The article describes the importance and actuality of control in the lessons of foreign languages nowadays. It also classifies and explains control functions, types, forms and its means.

Key words: *control, training function, controlling function, developing function, corrective function, generalising function, feedback, stimulating function, preliminary, current, thematic, intermediate, final, oral control, written control, test, control means.*

Today, a foreign language is seen as a way of knowing the world around us and self-development, a means of achieving professional fulfillment and success. This understanding of the role of a foreign language in modern life is reflected in the teaching of foreign languages.

The goals of teaching a foreign language are to develop communicative competence that allows a person to effectively and efficiently participate in the life of his native country and the world community.

In this regard, teaching a foreign language is considered as one of the priority areas of modern education. From a simple academic subject, it has become a basic element of the modern education system. The subject "Foreign Language" forms the student's communicative culture, contributes to his general speech development, broadening his horizons, forming ideas about the dialogue of cultures, and realizing himself as a bearer of the culture and spiritual values of his people.

The formation of foreign language communicative competence of students is a process of gradual and systematic mastery of its constituent competencies. The structure of the process of learning a foreign language implies the effective functioning of the feedback component, without which it is impossible to regulate and manage this process. Such a component is the control of the skills and abilities of the student.

The relevance of the problem of control is associated with the growing role of teaching a foreign language, with the achievement of certain successes in its practical implementation, due to which the scope of application of control has expanded, the possibilities of its positive influence on the educational and pedagogical process have

increased, and there are means for rationalizing the control itself as an integral part of this process.

In teaching a foreign language, control allows you to identify the level of formation of foreign language communicative competence of students at different stages of learning, to diagnose the difficulties that students may encounter in the process of learning a foreign language, to check the effectiveness of teaching methods and technologies.

Control in foreign language lessons can have different goals, but in all cases, it is not an end in itself and is educational in nature: it allows you to improve the learning process, replace ineffective teaching methods and methods with more effective ones, create more favorable conditions for correcting and improving practical language acquisition, to educate students by means of a foreign language.

A properly designed and organized control system allows you to objectively evaluate:

- learning activities of students.
- the quality of the teaching activity of the teacher, the effectiveness of the techniques and methods used in the learning process.

The main functions of the control system are divided into:

- training, aimed at acquiring new knowledge, the formation and development of skills and abilities in the process of performing control tasks, allowing you to clarify, correct, generalize, rethink the studied language and speech material;
- controlling, helping to determine the level of knowledge at a particular stage of learning and identifying gaps in mastering language and speech skills and abilities in various types of speech activity;
- developing / educational, allowing students to develop the ability to systematically carry out introspection of their own speech activity;
- corrective, including the explanation and demonstration of correct speech actions based on the results of the control, as well as the correction of the teaching activity of the teacher, the use of differentiation in teaching a foreign language;
- generalizing, implemented through the performance of control exercises in the process of summarizing and systematizing the material covered over a certain period of time;
- a feedback function that allows the teacher to manage the learning process based on and taking into account the opinions of students;
- stimulating, manifested in the activation of students' learning activities, including in the form of independent work, before the planned control.

The main types of control used in teaching a foreign language include input, current, thematic, intermediate and final control.

1. Input (preliminary) control allows you to make a starting cut and fix the initial level of knowledge of students. In addition, compare the initial entry level with the final one and measure the increase in knowledge, the degree of skills, abilities, competencies formed, analyze the dynamics and effectiveness of the learning process.

2. Current control is the most common and most effective type of control, designed to provide timely feedback and contribute to the intensification of the educational process.

3. Thematic control is carried out based on the results of mastering the thematic block of the educational and methodological complex, it seems possible to systematically carry it out due to the fact that the main principle of organizing educational material in a foreign language is the thematic principle.

4. Intermediate control is carried out in order to check the students' mastery of a large amount of material (for example, mastered in the academic quarter or half a year) and is designed to cut and fix the level of knowledge at the time of its implementation, as well as to determine the increase in knowledge, skills, abilities and the degree of formation of students' competencies .

5. The final control is carried out at the end of each year of study or upon completion of mastering a foreign language course and is aimed at identifying the achieved level of knowledge, determining the degree of formation of foreign language communicative competence of students.

Forms of educational control should be adequate to the competencies, the level of formation of which they check.

As part of a foreign language course, the following forms of control are used:

1. Oral control. It allows you to check the formation of the language, speech, sociocultural and compensatory competencies of students; at the same time, this form of control will be implemented not only in individual, but also in pair / group work of students, as well as through the implementation of project tasks with the subsequent presentation of the results achieved. In the oral form of verification, some difficulties may arise in fixing the volume of the statement and errors, which may be accidental due to the spontaneity of speech.

In the process of oral control, various technical means can be used, for example, a voice recorder or the capabilities of a digital language laboratory.

Oral control can be frontal, individual and group.

Frontal oral verification is most convenient for current control and for identifying the degree of assimilation or automation of the material. To identify the level of

formation of skills in monologue speech, it is effective to use an individual form of control. An example of this form of control is such a task as a monologue statement using supports (a situation, a studied topic, questions, drawings). Such a task is used, in particular, during the exam (section "Speaking"). Group control is also possible, when a group of students is involved in a conversation.

2. Written control is aimed primarily at checking the formation of the language and speech competencies of students, it is implemented in an individual form. The written form of control includes various kinds of written work.

The choice of the form of control in terms of the use of the native language depends on the purpose of the control.

3. Test as a specific form of control. Recently, the test method has become popular. According to many researchers, testing is a promising form of control that meets the requirements put forward by the modern education system. Testing allows you to quickly test your knowledge on one or more topics. Testing can be a form of both current and final control. However, this method should not be used all the time, as it cannot test students' creativity. Moreover, when performing test tasks, students can answer at random.

Control means are learning materials that are used to test the level of language proficiency. These include handouts, phonograms and videograms.

Handouts are cards with tasks that are used during classes to determine the readiness of students for educational activities and the level of knowledge of the material covered.

Audio materials are used for work in the language laboratory and in the regular classroom. They enable students to listen to an exemplary text, and if they have the necessary equipment, record their voice on tape and compare it with an exemplary one. Such a record becomes not only a material for analysis and evaluation by the teacher, but also an object of student self-control.

Drawings from a textbook and special teaching aids can be used as a visual support for performing a speech action according to the proposed program (answer questions for a drawing or a series of drawings, describe the content of the visual range, etc.).

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